

WAVE FORMATION IN AN ENCLOSED CONDUIT IN DIE CASTING

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ABSTRACT

Transition from a free surface flow to pressurized flow through hydraulic jump appears in several situations, which include the die casting cold chamber process, flow in sewer systems after a large rain storm, turbine tailraces, and in power plants during pipe failure. The study presented here is general, but with special interest in the application to a 10 billion die casting industry. One of the main problems in die casting is the product integrity due to porosity. Experiments have shown that there is a critical plunger velocity for which less air is entrained and thus the porosity is reduced. Earlier researchers approached this problem assuming that the energy is conserved. A comparison between the “energy conservation” model and the available experimental data presented here demonstrates that the energy is dissipated. Consequently, “the energy conservation” model under estimates the plunger velocity required for avoiding air entrainment. A model based on momentum conservation has been established, which is shown to be in a reasonable agreement with the limited available experimental data.

NOMENCLATURE

A Wetted shot sleeve cross section area
 Fr Froude number Rg/V_p^2
 h_1 Height of liquid at point 1
 h_2 Height of liquid at point 2
 H Height of shot sleeve height
 P_B Back pressure (runner)
 R Radius of the shot sleeve
 \tilde{v} Dimensionless velocity V_w/V_p
 v_1 Local velocity
 V_w Wave velocity in stationary coordinate
 V_p Plunger velocity in stationary coordinate

Greek Letters

γ Shape factor

Subscript

1 Associated with section 1
2 Associated with section 2
 c center of the cross section
 M momentum
 ε energy

Key Words

Moving hydraulic Jump, Die casting critical velocity, Critical plunger velocity, Die casting operating parameters, Turbulence, Jump conditions, Shot Sleeve.

1 Introduction

Transition of flow in a conduit from a free–surface flow to a pressurized flow occurs in several situations, such as sewer systems during large rainstorm events, turbine tailraces, and die casting. For instance, in the event of a large rainstorm, the flow in a sewer systems that starts as an open channel flow, can turn into pressurized flow (see fig. 1). This transition in a sewer system occurs because the system becomes incapable of discharging all the water. The flow is pressurized at a point downstream and creates a “geyser” (Cardle and Song 1988). The common approach is to assume that momentum is conserved. Yet, in the die casting industry the approach was to assume that “energy is conserved.”

The die casting is a process in which a liquid metal is injected into a form (die), which is opened after a short cooling period. Broadly speaking, the die casting is divided into two categories: cold chamber and hot chamber (see fig. 2 part A and B). The cold chamber is horizontal, while the hot chamber is vertical.

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These differences are significant because a vertical chamber requires heating and has a larger resistance (Bar-Meir, Eckert, and Goldstein 1996; Bar-Meir 1995a; Bar-Meir, Eckert, and Goldstein 1997). This paper deals with a cold chamber. The cold chamber is partially filled with liquid metal which is pushed into the form (to get a near net shape product) (see fig. 2 part A). This study is motivated by the need to improve the understanding and design of the die casting process.

Porosity is considered to be a major manufacturing problem encountered in many castings products. The porosity results from two different mechanisms: shrinkage porosity (difference between the liquid density and the solid density) and air/gas entrapment (gases are entrapped in the liquid metal). The porosity due to density change is not the concern here. Klein and Wimmer (1995) have shown that porosity due to entrapped gases constitutes a large portion of the total porosity. The main causes for gas/air entrapment are lubricant evaporation (reaction processes), incorrect placement of the vents, and insufficient vent area. The location of the gas/air entrapment is relevant and includes the shot sleeve, runner (connecting the conduit to the casting chamber), and the die (casting chamber). There research on gas/air entrapment in the runner is very limited. In fact, it is not known how to avoid it and this issue is still considered a knowledge gap. The entrainment in the die chamber is caused by the location(s), number and size of the vents. The size issue was introduced by (Bar-Meir 1995b). The locations is solved to a limited extent and it requires that the engineer to have experience and knowledge of fluid mechanics. Admittedly, beside experience in the engineering design of similar products and knowledge of fluid mechanics, this issue should be considered as unsolved. Discussions on the first three causes can be found elsewhere (Bar-Meir 2021b). The mixing mechanisms are attributed to three zones: the mold, runner, and the shot sleeve. In this study the mixing processes are analyzed in the shot sleeve. The gas/air entrapment in the shot sleeve is attributed to operational conditions for which a blockage of the gate by a liquid metal

FIGURE 2. Schematic of cold (A) and hot (B) chamber machine. various parts of the machine are exhibited like runner, gate, vents etc.

FIGURE 3. Schematic of wave formation in stationary coordinates

FIGURE 4. Schematic of wave formation in moving coordinates

FIGURE 1. Schematic of transition from free surface to pressurized flow in pipe with a "geyser."

wave occurs before the air is exhausted. In other words, the aim is to remove the air before the metal enters the die. Otherwise, the residual air is forced to mix with the liquid metal in the shot sleeve.

The significance of Air Entrainment in the Shot Sleeve (AESS) can be demonstrated by the large amounts of money given to this research by NSF, NADCA and others (Walkington 1996). There is no research known to the authors showing conclusively that AESS has been a prerequisite to the good production in the horizontal die casting machine. However, experience has shown that many engineers find this significant for reducing product porosity. The alternative "vertical shot sleeve" design results in a large resistance in the runner and requires a larger

machine for the same task (see fig. 2 part B). The vertical configuration also requires heating (a “hot chamber” machine). Thus, the production on the “cold chamber” (horizontal) machine is cheaper.

One possible remedy to remove air entrainment in a “cold chamber” machine is to operate with a complete filling of the shot sleeve. This, however, has three main shortfalls: the complete filling causes premature freezing in the runner entrance; it forces a cooler liquid to enter the molds prior to the hot liquid metal, thus may produce cold shots (frozen liquid metal enters the mold), and the casting cost is increased by the waste created by the extra casting. The die caster has a limited flexibility in selecting the diameter and the length of the shot sleeve. Therefore, major manufactures of die casting machinery try to patent a variety of velocity functions to their plunger aiming to control the wave growth, and thus eliminating gas entrainment (Young and Brissing 1993).

Garber (1982) reported on a critical plunger velocity he observed in his experiments of water injection. He also built a model, which is based on energy conservation, to calculate the critical plunger velocity¹.

The shape of the created wave, resembles a hydraulic jump. The hydraulic jump was extensively investigated by civil and mechanical engineers. Bélanger modeled the two dimensional hydraulic jump (Bélanger 1828). Later, Bakhmeteff and Matzke (1936) modeled the energy dissipation among other phenomena. Since then, various parameters, such as the surface profiles, mean averaged velocities and turbulence characteristics for the various flow regions have been studied extensively for a two dimensional hydraulic jump (in a rectangular and a trapezoid conduit cross section), see for example (Madsen and Svendsen 1983) and (Rajaratnam 1967).

The conventional approach to model a hydraulic jump is to assume that energy is lost due the formation of eddies and therefore, the momentum conservation principle is applied. In this study, a criterion for transition from a free surface flow to pressurized flow in conduits is established.

The previous solution based on energy conservation and the current momentum conservation solution are compared with available experimental data (Garber 1982; Karni 1991). The criteria are formulated in a simple easy-to-use form, which can be applied by die casters to help in the design of die casting processes.

2 The Model

Consider a duct (or any cross section) with a liquid at level h_2 and a plunger moving from the left to the right, as shown in fig. 3. Experiments (Brissing 1999; Karni 1991) have shown that after

¹. This model was taught exclusively until recently (~2000) in the die casting casting industry (Walkington 2000).
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a short transition period, a quasi steady flow is established. A typical developing distance is of the order of the tube diameter. There is a unique height, h_1 and a unique wave velocity, V_w for every constant plunger velocity, V_p . The liquid in the substrate ahead of the wave is still, its height, h_2 is determined by the initial fill. Once the height, h_1 is exceeds the height of the shot sleeve, H there will be splashing. The splashing occurs because no equilibrium can be achieved. For h_1 smaller than H , a reflecting wave from the opposite wall appears, which affects an enhanced air entrainment. Thus, the preferred situation is when $h_1 = H$, in which case no splashing or a reflecting wave results.

It is easier to model the system in coordinates which moves with the wave velocity, as shown in Fig. 4. In the moving coordinates, the wave is stationary, the plunger moves back at a velocity $(V_w - V_p)$ and the liquid moves from the right to the left. The dashed line shows the stationary control volume.

Mass conservation of the liquid in the control volume yields

$$\int_{A_2} \rho V_w dA = \int_{A_1} \rho (V_w - v_1) dA \quad (1)$$

where v_1 is the local velocity. Under quasi-steady state conditions, the corresponding averaged velocity equals the plunger velocity (when $h_1 = H$):

$$\bar{v}_1 = \frac{1}{A_1} \int_{A_1} v_1 dA = V_p \quad (2)$$

The heat transfer processes can be neglected because of the short process duration (Eckert 1989). Therefore, the density of the liquid metal (which is a function of the temperature) can be assumed constant). Under the above assumptions, eq. (1) can be simplified

$$V_w A(h_2) = (V_w - V_p) A(h_1); \quad (3)$$

where:

$$A(h_i) = \int_0^{h_i} dA$$

The index i is either 1 or 2 for the specific cross section. Thus,

$$f(h_1, h_2) = \frac{V_w}{V_w - V_p} \quad (4)$$

where $f(h_1, h_2) = A(h_1)/A(h_2)$ is dimensionless ratio function of h_1 and h_2 . Equation (4) can be transformed into dimensionless

from:

$$f(h_1, h_2) = \frac{\tilde{v}}{\tilde{v} - 1} \quad (5a)$$

Or rearranging it to be

$$\tilde{v} = \frac{f(h_1, h_2)}{f(h_1, h_2) - 1} \quad (5b)$$

where $\tilde{v} = V_w/V_p$

3 Energy Conservation

Assuming energy is conserved and under conditions of the negligible heat transfer, the energy conservation equation (Bar-Meir 2021a) for the liquid in the control volume (see Fig. 4) yields:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{A_1} \left[\frac{P_1}{\rho} + \frac{\gamma_{1\epsilon} (V_w - V_p)^2}{2} \right] (V_w - V_p) dA \\ = \int_{A_2} \left[\frac{P_2}{\rho} + \frac{V_w^2}{2} \right] V_w dA \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where the dimensionless parameter $\gamma_{1\epsilon}$ (see Appendix B) is

$$\gamma_{1\epsilon} = \frac{1}{A_1 (V_w - V_p)^3} \int_{A_1} (V_w - v_1)^3 dA \quad (7)$$

Note that the gravity term gz included in the pressure term (Bar-Meir 2021a).

The shape factor, $\gamma_{1\epsilon}$ is introduced to account for the velocity deviation at section 1 from a pure plug flow. Note that in die casting, the flow is pushed by the plunger, and can be considered as inlet flow into a duct. The typical Re number is 10^5 (Eckert 1989) and for this value the entry length is greater than $50[m]$, which is larger than any shot sleeve by at least two orders of magnitude. Thus, a plug flow can be assumed at the rear section of the wave, whereby $\gamma_{1\epsilon} = 1$.

The pressure in the gas phase can be assumed to be constant. The hydrostatic pressure in the liquid can be represented by $R\bar{y}_c g \rho$ (Rajaratnam 1965), where $R\bar{y}_c$ is the center of the cross section area². For a circular cross section, it is given by

²A new method to calculate the centroid was developed by this understanding by this understanding long after this article was written (Bar-Meir 2021c) page 109.

eq. (8a) $h_2 < R$ and eq. (8b) for $h_2 < R$ (see fig. 5):

$$\bar{y}_{c2} = \left[1 - \frac{2/3 \sin^3 \theta}{\pi - \theta + \sin \theta \cos \theta} \right] \quad (8a)$$

$$\bar{y}_{c2} = \left[1 - \frac{2/3 \sin^3 \theta}{\theta - \sin \theta \cos \theta} \right] \quad (8b)$$

For a constant liquid density, eq. (6) can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \left[R\bar{y}_{c1} g + \gamma_{1\epsilon} \frac{(V_w - V_p)^2}{2} \right] (V_w - V_p) A(h_1) = \\ \left[R\bar{y}_{c1} g V_p^2 + \frac{V_w^2}{2} \right] V_w A(h_2) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Rearranging eq. (9) yields

$$\begin{aligned} f(h_1, h_2) \left[\frac{R\bar{y}_{c1} g}{V_p^2} + \gamma_{1\epsilon} \frac{(v-1)^2}{2} \right] (\tilde{v} - 1) = \\ \left[\frac{R\bar{y}_{c2} g}{V_p^2} + \frac{v^2}{2} \right] \tilde{v} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The Froude number is defined as

$$\mathbf{Fr} = \frac{Rg}{V_p^2} \quad (11)$$

Combining eq. (5a) with eq. (10) and utilizing the definition of the Froude number provides

$$2\mathbf{Fr}_\epsilon \bar{y}_{c1} + \gamma_{1\epsilon} (\tilde{v} - 1)^2 = 2\mathbf{Fr}_\epsilon \bar{y}_{c2} + \tilde{v}^2 \quad (12)$$

Substituting eq. (5b) into eq. (12), the later can be further rearranged as

$$\mathbf{Fr}_\epsilon = \frac{(1 + \gamma_\epsilon) f(h_1, h_2)}{2(\bar{y}_{c1} - \bar{y}_{c2})} - \gamma_{1\epsilon} \quad (13)$$

Note, that when the liquid reaches the shot sleeve crown, $h_1 = H = 2R$ and $\bar{y}_{c1} = 1$. Given the substrate height, eq. (13) can be solved for the \mathbf{Fr} , and the corresponding plunger velocity is defined by eq. (11). This solution will be referred herein as the “energy solution.” However, energy is known to dissipate in a hydraulic jump, in which case the equal sign is in eq. (13) does

FIGURE 5. Schematic of the cross section

not apply and the criterion for the non-splashing operation would read

$$Fr_\epsilon > Fr_{\text{optimal}} \quad (14)$$

4 Momentum Equation

In this section the momentum conservation principle is applied to the control volume in fig. 4. For large Re ($\sim 10^5$), the wall shear stress can be neglected compared to the inertial terms (the wave width is assumed to have a negligible length). The momentum balance reads

$$\int_{A_1} [P_1 + \rho \gamma_{1M} (V_w - V_p)^2] dA = \int_{A_2} [P_2 + \rho V_w^2] dA \quad (15)$$

where

$$\gamma_{1M} = \frac{1}{A_1 (V_w - V_p)^2} \int_{A_1} (V_w - v_1)^2 dA = \frac{1}{A_1 (\bar{v} - 1)^2} \int_{A_1} \left(\bar{v} - \frac{v_1}{V_p} \right)^2 dA \quad (16)$$

Given the velocity profile, v_1 , the shape factor γ_{1M} can be obtained in terms of \bar{v} . For a plug flow $\gamma_{1M} = 1$. The expressions for γ_{1M} for laminar and turbulent velocity profiles at section 1 are given in the appendix. Based on the assumptions used in the previous section, eq. (15) reads:

$$\left[R \bar{y}_{c1} g + \gamma_{1M} (V_w - V_p)^2 \right] A(h_1) = \left[\bar{y}_{c2} g + V_w^2 \right] A(h_2) \quad (17)$$

Rearranging eq. (17) into dimensionless form provides

$$f(h_1, h_2) \left[\bar{y}_{c1} Fr + \gamma_{1M} (\bar{v} - 1)^2 \right] = \bar{y}_{c2} Fr + \bar{v}^2 \quad (18)$$

FIGURE 6. The critical Froude number as a function of the relative height

Combining eq. (18) with eq. (5b) yields

$$Fr_M = \frac{\left(\frac{f(h_1, h_2)}{f(h_1, h_2) - 1} \right)^2 - \gamma_{1M} f(h_1, h_2) \left[\frac{f(h_1, h_2)}{f(h_1, h_2) - 1} - 1 \right]^2}{f(h_1, h_2) \bar{y}_{c1} - \bar{y}_{c2}} \quad (19)$$

where Fr_M is the Fr number which evolves from the momentum conservation equation. Equation (19) is the analogue to eq. (13) and will be referred herein as the “the momentum solution.”

5 Results and Discussion

It has been demonstrated that the solutions of the “momentum solution” and the “energy solution” can be presented in a simple form. Moreover, these solutions can be applied to any shape of the cross section (square, trapezoid, etc) the transition of the free surface flow to pressurized flow. The discussion here focuses on the circular cross section, since it is the only one used by die casters and it is the most common in a sewer system. Solutions for other velocity profiles, such as laminar flow (Poiseuille’s parabolic flow) are discussed in the appendix. Note that the Froude number is based on the plunger velocity, and not on the upstream velocity as commonly used in the two dimensional hydraulic jump.

The experimental data obtained by Garber (1982), Karni (1991) and the predicted transition from the free surface flow to pressurized flow (obtained by equation eq. (13) and eq. (19) for a circular cross section assuming a plug flow profile), are presented in fig. 6. The “two plates” analysis (two dimensional) of

the hydraulic jump (where the shape factors of the velocity profiles are considered) is presented also in fig. 6. The agreement between Garber’s experimental results and the “momentum solution” (with exception of one point at $(h_2 = R)$) is reasonable.

The experimental results reported by Karni were taken when the critical velocity was obtained (liquid reached the pipe crown), while the experimental results from Garber are interpretation (kind of average) of subcritical velocities and supercritical velocities, with the exception of one point at $h_2/R = 1.3$ (which is very closed to the “momentum solution”). Hence, it is reasonable to assume that the accuracy of Karni’s measurements is better than Garber’s results. However, these data points have to be taken with some caution. None of the experimental data sets were checked if steady state was achieved and it is not clear how the measurements were carried out.

It is widely accepted that in the two dimensional hydraulic jump small and large eddies are created, which are responsible for the large energy dissipation (Henderson 1996). Therefore, energy conservation can not be used to describe hydraulic jump heights. This statement is true regardless of the cross section shape. In fact, the further from a circular shape, the more energy is lost. Thus, the plunger velocity has to be greater than the one obtained by “the energy solution”, as suggested by the results in fig. 6. The results obtained indicate that the critical Froude number for the “energy solution” is larger than the Froude number obtained in the experimental results. The Froude number inversely proportional to square of the plunger velocity, $Fr \propto 1/V_p^2$, hence the critical velocity is smaller. The “energy solution” therefore underestimates the plunger velocity. The “two plates solution” is in reasonable agreement with the “momentum solution” for relatively low initial liquid holdups (i.e., for $h_2/R < 0.6$). For higher initial liquid holdups the cross section the “two plates solution” requires smaller Froude number, and therefore over estimates the critical plunger velocity. This can be explained by the fact that less material needed is to lifted up in the circular cross section and therefore less energy required.

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Concluding Remarks

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FIGURE A.1. γ_{1M} as a function of dimensionless height h_2

Appendix A

The specification of the velocity profile in the wave core is required for calculations the shape factors defined in equations (7) and (16). The calculations of the shape factors for velocity profiles, are demonstrated here by considering two typical cases. For the case of $h_1 = 2R$, a fully developed laminar velocity profile is given by:

$$\frac{v(\tilde{r})}{V_p} = 2 [1 - \tilde{r}^2] \quad (20)$$

The turbulent velocity profile can be represented by power 7th-law profile

$$\frac{v(\tilde{r})}{V_p} = 1.224 [1 - \tilde{r}]^{1/7} \quad (21)$$

where $\tilde{r} = r/R$ and note the V_p is the average velocity of the liquid the full cross section. Utilizing the definition, γ_{1M} , in eq. (16), the momentum shape factor for the laminar flow is

$$\gamma_{1M} = \frac{2}{(\tilde{v} - 1)^2} \int_0^1 [\tilde{v} - 2 + 2\tilde{r}^2]^2 \tilde{r} d\tilde{r} = \frac{\tilde{v}^2 - 2\tilde{v} + 4/3}{(\tilde{v} - 1)^2} \quad (22)$$

The corresponding shape factor for turbulent flow is given by

$$\gamma_{1M} = \frac{2}{(\bar{v}-1)^2} \int_0^1 \left[\bar{v} - 1.224(1-\bar{v})^{1/7} \right]^2 \bar{r} d\bar{r} = \frac{\bar{v}^2 - 2\bar{v} + 50/49}{(\bar{v}-1)^2} \quad (23)$$

Figure A.1 exhibits the shape factor for laminar and turbulent flows in a circular conduit, and the shape factor obtained for 2D turbulent. For $h_2 \rightarrow 2R$ the shape factor approaches the value of 50/49 and 4/3 for energy conservation. As shown in the figure, the change from a very fast plug flow to laminar flow, requires large shape factor.

When the wave does not reach the crown of the sleeve, $h_1 < 2R$, the velocity profile is a complicated function of the location in the flow cross sectional area. Analytical solution for the case of the laminar flow can be obtained in terms of the Fourier integrals using Bipolar coordinate system (Brauner, Rovinsky, and Maron 1996). An approximated shape factor for a partially filled sleeve can however be obtained by describing the velocity profile along the conduit center line as a channel flow. For turbulent flow, the seventh power power law velocity profile for this case is:

$$\frac{v_1(\bar{r})}{V_p} = \frac{v_1(\bar{y})}{V_p} = \frac{8}{7} \bar{y}^{1/7} \quad (24)$$

where $\bar{y} = y/h_1$ and the corresponding shape factor reads:

$$\gamma_{1M} = \frac{1}{(\bar{v}-1)} \int_0^1 \left[\bar{v} - 8/7(\bar{y})^{1/7} \right]^2 = \frac{\bar{v}^2 - 2\bar{v} + 64/63}{(\bar{v}-1)^2} \quad (25)$$

This is the shape factor for a fully developed turbulent channel flow. It can be considered a reasonable approximation for the shape factor for turbulent flow in a partially filled tube with $h_1/R \sim 30\% - 70\%$.

Appendix B

Equation (6) shows a common substitution and it was requested to provide an explanation for it. The complicated part of the energy equation is

$$\int_A \frac{(v(h) - V_p)^3}{2} dA(h) \quad (26)$$

In this integral, there is no specific requirement on the way the velocity profile function is presented. In fact, h is generally a 2-dimensional function. Equation eq. (26) can be rearranged and combined to be

$$\int_A \overbrace{\frac{(v(h) - V_p)^3}{(V_w - V_p)^3}}^{\gamma''} \frac{(V_w - V_p)^3}{2} dA(h) \quad (27)$$

The γ is the core integrate of the integral. In doing this manipulation (while not solving), one creates a kind of object oriented approach.

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